

XMM-Newton : a pathfinder for future multi-wavelength and multi-messenger observations with Athena

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Work Package WP6 Spectra

Deliverable D6.3 Fitting products for all sources

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1 Introduction

In this work, done within work package six of the EU funded XMM2Athena project, we built low resolution X-ray spectra using the count-rates in the five energy bands defined in the 4XMM catalogue (with energy limits 0.2-0.5 keV, 0.5-1 keV, 1-2 keV, 2-4.5 keV and 4.5-12 keV) and fitted an absorbed power-law model to all detections in the 4XMM-DR11 catalogue. We provide best fit parameter values, confidence intervals and full probability distributions. In the previous delivered catalogues (D6.1 and D6.2) the starting point was using sources with spectral products in the XMM-Newton archive. For this deliverable we have produced spectral fits for all detections in the 4XMM-DR11. All issues that we encountered during the fitting are described below and flagged in the catalogue.

2 Data and analysis

2.1 Data: Construction of count-rate spectra

We used the detection count-rates from the 4XMM-DR11 catalogue to build X-ray spectra for the 895 415 detections included in the catalogue. Using the count-rates in the five defined energy bands (0.2-0.5, 0.5-1, 1-2, 2-4.5, 4.5-12 keV) for each EPIC camera (MOS1, MOS2 and pn), along with proper response matrices (RMF and ARF, see below), we obtained a set of data equivalent to very low resolution X-ray spectra. In other words, this technique is roughly equivalent to extracting an X-ray spectrum and grouping it in five bins corresponding to the 4XMM energy bands. These spectra can be analysed using the standard software and techniques of X-ray astronomy. Using this method we are able to give at least a crude estimate for the spectral parameters of all sources in the 4XMM-DR11, even in those cases where, given the low number of counts, a proper X-ray spectrum was not extracted.

For each of these low resolution spectra, we used as RMF the canned matrix calculated by the XMM-Newton calibration team for the corresponding detector, epoch and mode of the observation.¹ As ARF matrices we calculated a set of matrices using the `arfgen` SAS tool, one per camera and filter (Thin, Medium and Thick). We took into account that the count-rates are already corrected of vignetting, detector efficiency, PSF losses, bad pixels and CCD gaps, so none of these effects are included in the ARF generation. The count-rates are background-subtracted, so no background spectra are needed.

2.2 Fitting

We used Python scripts to perform the automated fits making use of the fitting and modelling software packages Xspec 12.11.1d (Arnaud 1996) and Sherpa 4.14.0 (Freeman et al., 2001), and the analysis software BXA (Bayesian X-ray Analysis; Buchner et al., 2014). For each detection, data of all available cameras were fitted at once.

¹<https://www.cosmos.esa.int/web/xmm-newton/epic-response-files>

BXA uses a nested sampling algorithm (UltraNest, Buchner 2021) to sample the posterior distribution given the likelihood of the data and a certain set of priors for the values of the parameters. In our case the likelihood probability is estimated through the χ^2 value for a set of model parameters ($\log L = -\chi^2/2$). By construction our count-rate spectra are binned, background subtracted X-ray spectra, so no other statistic, more suited for Poisson-distributed data (e.g. Cash C-statistic), can be employed. Note also that for sources with very low count-rates some of the bins in our spectra have less than 20 counts, and therefore a χ^2 statistic is not correct from a statistical point of view (Cash 1979). Hence, be aware that our procedure only gives a quick, rough estimate of the posterior distribution of the spectral parameters. For more rigorous results, a proper X-ray spectral modelling should be done. In those cases where the source is included in the D6.1 or D6.2 catalogues, we strongly recommend using those results.

2.3 Spectral model

As source model we used an absorbed power-law model (TBabs*powerlaw in Xspec). In case the object is observed by pn and MOS detectors, an inter-instrument normalisation constant is included for the MOS spectra. If MOS1 and MOS2 spectra are available, the constant is the same for both MOS detectors. Variable parameters are the logarithm of the hydrogen column density of the absorber, which is allowed to vary between 20 and 26 $\log_{10}(\text{cm}^{-2})$, the power-law photon index, which can vary between 0 and 6, the logarithm of the power-law normalization, which can vary between -8 and 3, and the inter-instrument normalisation in all cases defined as pn/MOS that is constrained to be between 0 and 5. BXA requires the setting of a probability prior for each free parameter in the model. We used flat priors for all four parameters.

2.4 Best-fit parameters and error computation

The UltraNest algorithm implemented in BXA gives the marginalized posterior probability distribution for all free parameters in the fitted model. We used these distributions to estimate the best-fit parameters and the corresponding errors. For each free parameter we provide the median with percentiles of 5 and 95 per cent. Furthermore the mode, calculated using a half sample algorithm (Robertson and Cryer, 1974) that makes use of functions from Henry Freudenriech (Hughes STX) statistics library (called ROBLIB) from AstroIDL User's Library, with the 90 per cent highest probability density interval (which corresponds to the narrowest interval that includes 90 per cent of the probability), calculated using Chen-Shao algorithm (Chen et al., 2000), is provided.

2.5 Goodness of fit

We used the χ^2 value for the best-fit model parameters as an estimation of the goodness of fit. We calculated the corresponding p-values for the fit, and any model showing a p-value ≥ 0.01 is considered as an acceptable fit. We also include the reduced χ^2 value (the ratio between the best-fit χ^2 value and the degrees of freedom of the model) in the model. The usual rule-of-thumb for a good fit is that the reduced χ^2 should be around one. Nevertheless, be aware of the possible caveats we

Figure 1: Distribution of p-values of the best-fit models for the total catalogue (grey) and the clean sample (red).

mentioned above about using the χ^2 statistic for these count-rate spectra, particularly in low count detections.

3 Results

We fitted the 895 415 detections included in the 4XMM-DR11 catalogue, obtaining an acceptable fit for 89.7% of them. Since we did not include any filtering in our selection, the catalogue can include a non negligible number of spurious sources, detections in problematic fields or with other observational issues. We defined a “clean” sample by selecting detections with $\text{SUM_FLAG} \leq 1$, $\text{OBS_CLASS} \leq 3$ and $\text{EP_8_DET_ML} \geq 10$. Moreover, the spectral model we selected is reasonably flexible for AGN sources, but not so well suited for other X-ray populations, like clusters, hot stars, neutron stars, X-ray binaries, etc. In order to minimise the non-AGN contamination in the clean sample, we also included only sources with $\text{EP_EXTENT_ML} \leq 1$ and above the galactic plane ($|\text{BII}| > 20$), where the bulk of the stellar population is concentrated. Thus 372 695 detections remain within this clean sample, with 95.8% of them having an acceptable fit. In Fig. 1 we show the distribution of the χ^2 p-values for these samples.

In Figs. 2, 3 and 4 we show the distribution of the best-fit spectral parameters (median and mode values for photon index, Hydrogen column density and Inter-instrument normalisation, respectively),

Figure 2: Distribution of the photon index for the best-fit models. Colours as in Fig. 1.

Figure 3: Distribution of the Hydrogen column density for the best-fit models. Colours as in Fig. 1.

for the full catalogue (grey) and for the clean sample (red). In both samples, the photon index distribution is concentrated around $\Gamma = 2$, as expected for a population dominated by AGN (Nandra & Pounds, 1994). The mode distribution for the full sample show a non-negligible number of sources in the extremes of our selected photon-index interval. The spectral model we used here is probably not adequate for these ultrahard/ultrasoft sources. In the clean sample, targeted for selecting AGN, these peaks in the interval extremes almost disappear.

The Inter-instrument normalization (IIN) constant is introduced to take into account possible inaccuracies in the cross-calibration of XMM-Newton cameras. These effects should be small and the expected value of the IIN should be around one. Figure 4 shows that this is the case for the bulk of our results. Nevertheless there is a non-negligible number of detections with IIN significantly far from one, even when considering only acceptable fits. We found the same result during the production of D6.1. In the corresponding report we discussed in detail the possible causes of this issue. We found that problematic, possibly spurious, sources with $SUM_FLAG > 0$ are a major cause of this problem. As shown in Fig. 4, in the clean sample, where most of these sources were filtered out, the number of detections with extreme IINs is reduced.

Figure 4: Distribution of the Inter-instrument normalisation for the best-fit models. Colours as in Fig. 1

3.1 Description of the columns

Our catalogue contains one row for each detection, and 89 columns containing information about the source detection and the spectral-fitting results. Not available values are represented by an empty “nan” (or “null”) value. The first 53 columns contain information about the source and observation, then the following 36 columns contain, goodness of fit and related flags, and the parameter values and errors.

3.1.1 Source and observation

- **DETID:** A unique identifier, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **OBS_ID:** The XMM-Newton observation identification, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **SRC_NUM:** The (hexadecimal) source number in the individual source list for this observation (OBS_ID).
- **RA:** Right Ascension, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **DEC:** Declination, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **LII:** Galactic longitude, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **BII:** Galactic latitude, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **EP_8_FLUX:** EPIC flux for the 0.2-12 keV band, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **EP_8_DET_ML:** Detection likelihood for the 0.2-12 keV band considering all available EPIC data, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **EP_EXTENT_ML:** Likelihood for the source being extended, considering all available EPIC data, as in 4XMM-DR11.

The following set of columns is given for both the pn and MOS detectors that contribute to a detection. If one of them does not contribute the values are set to “nan”. “DET” can be “PN”, “M1” or “M2”, and “EBAND” can be 1, 2, 3, 4 or 5, corresponding to the five energy bands defined in the 4XMM catalogue.

- **DET_EBAND_RATE:** Count-rate, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **DET_EBAND_RATE_ERR:** Count-rate error, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **DET_MASKFRAC:** Entries from the “DET_MASKFRAC” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **DET_FLAG:** Entries from the “DET_FLAG” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.

The following set of columns summarize other flags related to the detection and the observation:

- **EP_FLAG:** Entries from the “EP_FLAG” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **SUM_FLAG:** Entries from the “SUM_FLAG” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **CONFUSED:** Entries from the “DET_MASKFRAC” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **OBS_CLASS:** Entries from the “DET_MASKFRAC” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.
- **HIGH_BACKGROUND:** Entries from the “DET_FLAG” column, as in 4XMM-DR11.

3.1.2 Fitting statistics

- **logz:** Evidence of the posterior, calculated through Ultranest.
- **chi2:** χ^2 value for the best-fit model parameters.
- **dof:** Degrees of freedom of the source fit.
- **rchi2:** Reduced χ^2 (χ^2 / dof).
- **pvalue:** p-value of the fit given its χ^2 and dof values.
- **flag:** The flag values were selected in a manner consistent with the D6.1 catalogue.
 - 4: Formally unacceptable fit ($\text{pvalue} < 0.01$);
 - 0: None of the previous issues occurred.

3.1.3 Model related columns

In the last 29 columns we give for each of the four free parameters, and the associated observed flux, the median and mode with the corresponding lower and upper boundaries for 90% intervals. Possible parameters names are: logNH (logarithm of the hydrogen column density of the absorber, in units of $\log_{10}(\text{cm}^{-2})$), PhoIndex (photon index), logNorm (logarithm of the power-law normalization), IIN (inter-instrument normalisation), and logflux (logarithm of the flux in the 0.2 to 12 keV band, in units of $\log_{10}(\text{erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1})$).

- **PARAMETER_med:** Median of the parameter value.
- **PARAMETER_med_min, PARAMETER_med_max:** Percentiles of 5 and 95 per cent.
- **PARAMETER_mod:** Mode of the parameter value.
- **PARAMETER_mod_min, PARAMETER_mod_max:** Lower and upper limits of the 90 per cent credible interval for the parameter.

3.2 Fluxes

We compare the 0.2-12 keV (8 band) fluxes included in 4XMM DR11 with the fluxes calculated from our count-rate spectral fits (median and mode estimates). Figure 5 shows the comparison for the whole catalogue (top), and for our clean sample (bottom), including only detections where our fit is considered acceptable ($p\text{-value} > 0.01$). In each case we calculated the Spearman rank correlation coefficient (ρ) to have a quantitative estimate of the agreement between both methods. In both samples the bulk of the population is distributed along the 1-to-1 line, and they are strongly correlated ($\rho > 0.8$). For most cases our method gives similar fluxes to the 4XMM catalogue, but there are a significant number of detections with clear differences. This effect is much reduced in the clean sample, but there is still some scatter. Given that the 4XMM fluxes are calculated assuming a single spectral model, an absorbed power-law with $\text{NH} = 3 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $\Gamma = 1.7$ (Webb et al. 2020), this effect is expected. Our spectral modelling is more flexible for reproducing the spectral shapes of different sources, so we expect that our method gives more accurate flux estimates in cases where the actual spectrum deviates significantly from the one assumed in the 4XMM.

3.3 Comparison with D6.1 results

As part of WP6, we run proper spectral fits for all the 4XMM-DR10 detections with good spectral products in the XMM-Newton archive (D6.1). All these sources are also included in the catalogue we are presenting here, so we can do a comparison between the spectral parameters we obtained using the count-rate spectra and those provided in D6.1. Figures 6, 7, 8, 9 show this comparison for all the sources included in both D6.1 and D6.3, and for the sources in the clean sample we defined above also included in D6.1 and with reliable fits in both catalogues (flag == 0 for both).

We found a good agreement between both methods in the case of the X-ray fluxes (Fig. 6), particularly in the case of the clean sample. For the photon index and NH (Fig. 7 and 8) the correlation

Figure 5: Comparison between 4XMM DR11 fluxes and count-rate fits fluxes for the full catalogue (top) and the clean sample (bottom). The colormap shows the density of sources in the regions. Red contours enclose 90% of the total sample in each panel. Red dotted lines show the one-to-one relation. Fluxes in CGS units.

Figure 6: Comparison between the fluxes obtained using a proper spectral fit (D6.1) and using count-rate spectra (D6.3), for the full catalogue (top) and the clean sample (bottom). Symbols and colours as in Fig. 5.

Figure 7: Comparison between the photon index obtained using a proper spectral fit (D6.1) and using count-rate spectra (D6.3), for the full catalogue (top) and the clean sample (bottom). Symbols and colours as in Fig. 5.

Figure 8: Comparison between the Hydrogen column density obtained using a proper spectral fit (D6.1) and using count-rate spectra (D6.3), for the full catalogue (top) and the clean sample (bottom). Symbols and colours as in Fig. 5.

Figure 9: Comparison between the IIN obtained using a proper spectral fit (D6.1) and using count-rate spectra (D6.3), for the full catalogue (top) and the clean sample (bottom). Symbols and colours as in Fig. 5.

is reasonable, but there is significant scatter. The agreement between methods doesn't seem to improve when using the clean sample. The plots for these two parameters show a large accumulation of sources in the limits of the parameter space. This is caused by sources where in one method the posterior distribution of the parameter is reasonably constrained, but the other method cannot. Sources with poorly constrained posteriors can be identified in the catalogue through large credible intervals for the parameter of interest. Given the simple model we are using here, the cause of a poorly constrained posterior is due to low count statistics, where the number of source counts is close to the background level.

Figure 9 shows the comparison for the IIN. While the bulk of detections is concentrated, as expected, around one, the results of both method are weakly correlated, although there is some improvement when using the clean sample. It is worth mentioning that in the case of D6.1 MOS spectra were combined into a single spectrum. This could result in changes for the expected value of the IIN.

In summary, these results show that our method of using count-rate spectra for the estimation of spectral parameters can be a reasonable approach for population studies, after a reasonable filtering of the catalogue. For studies of individual sources, the extraction and fitting of a proper spectrum is the most recommendable approach.

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²<http://www.astropy.org>

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